

Parallel Solvers for Incompressible Navier-Stokes Equations and Scalable Tools for FEM Applications

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Abstract

The White Paper content is focused on: a) construction and analysis of novel scalable algorithms to enhance scientific applications based on mesh methods (mainly on finite element method (FEM) technology); b) optimization of a new class of algorithms on many core systems.

From one site, the commonly accepted benchmark problem in computational fluid dynamics (CFD) – time dependent system of incompressible Navier-Stokes equations, is considered. The activities were motivated by advanced large-scale simulations of turbulent flows in the atmosphere and in the ocean, simulation of multiphase flows in order to extract average statistics, solving subgrid problems as part of homogenization procedures etc. The computer model is based on implementation of a new class of parallel numerical methods and algorithms for time dependent problems. It only requires solution of tridiagonal linear systems and therefore it is computationally very efficient, with a computational complexity of the same order as that of an explicit scheme, and yet, unconditionally stable. The scheme is particularly convenient for parallel implementation. Among the most important novel ideas is to avoid the transposition which is usually used in alternating directions time stepping algorithms. The final goal is to provide portable tools for integration in commonly accepted codes like Elmer and OpenFOAM. The new development software is organized as a computer library for using of researchers dealing with solution of incompressible Navier-Stokes equations

From other hand, we implement and develop new scalable algorithms and software for FEM simulations with typically $O(10^9)$ degrees of freedom in space for an IBM Blue Gene/P computer. We have considered voxel and unstructured meshes; stationary and time dependent problems; linear and nonlinear models. The performed work was focused on the development of scalable mesh methods, and tuning of the related software tools mainly to the IBM Blue Gene/P architecture but other massively parallel computers and MPI clusters were taken into account too. Efficient algorithms for time stepping, mesh refinement and parallel mappings were implemented. The aim here is again providing software tools for integration in Elmer and OpenFOAM. The computational models address discrete problems in the range of $O(10^9)$ degrees of freedom in space. The related time stepping techniques and iterative solvers are targeted to meet the Tier-1 and (further) Tier-0 requirements.

Scalability on 512 IBM Blue Gene/P nodes and several other high performance computing clusters is currently documented for the tested software modules and some of them are presented in this paper. Comparison results of running Elmer code on Intel cluster (16 cores, Intel Xeon X5560) and on IBM Blue Gene/P computer can be found. Variants of 1D, 2D and 3D domain partitioning for the 3D test problems were systematically analysed showing the advantages of the 3D partitioning for the Blue Gene/P communication system.

1. New parallel solver for incompressible Navier–Stokes equations on massively parallel computers

1.1. Introduction

Traditionally, the supercomputers are used very actively in the Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) and the modules for solving Navier-Stokes equations are among the basic tools. The objective here is to analyze the parallel performance of a novel fractional time stepping technique, based on a direction splitting strategy, developed to solve the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations.

Projection schemes were first introduced in [4, 15] and they have been used in Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) for about 40 years. During these years, such techniques went through some evolution, but the main paradigm, consisting of decomposing vector fields into a divergence-free part and a gradient, has been preserved (see [6] for a review of projection methods). In terms of computational efficiency, projection algorithms are far superior to the methods that solve the coupled velocity-pressure system. This feature makes them the most popular techniques in the CFD community for solving the unsteady Navier-Stokes equations. The computational complexity of each time step of the projection methods is that of solving one vector-valued advection-diffusion equation, plus one scalar-valued Poisson equation with Neumann boundary conditions. For large scale problems and for large Reynolds numbers the cost of solving the Poisson equation in this algorithm becomes dominant.

The alternating directions algorithm proposed in [7] reduces the computational complexity of the action of the incompressibility constraint. The key idea is to modify the projection paradigm, in which the vector fields are decomposed into a divergence-free part plus a gradient part. Departure from the standard projection methods has been proved to be very efficient for solving variable density flows (see, for instance [8, 9]). In the new method the pressure equation is derived from a perturbed form of the continuity equation, in which the incompressibility constraint is penalized in a negative norm induced by the direction splitting. The standard Poisson problem for the pressure correction is replaced by series of one-dimensional second-order boundary value problems. This technique is proved to be stable and convergent; for details see [7].

1.2. Description of the algorithm

The time-dependent Navier-Stokes equations on a finite time interval $[0, T]$, and in a space domain $\Omega = (0, 1)^3$:

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t \mathbf{u} - \nu \Delta \mathbf{u} + \nabla p &= \mathbf{f} && \text{in } \Omega \times [0, T], \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} &= 0 && \text{in } \Omega \times [0, T], \\ \mathbf{u}|_{\partial\Omega} &= 0 && \text{in } [0, T] \text{ and } \mathbf{u}|_{t=0} = \mathbf{u}_0 \text{ in } \Omega, \end{aligned} \quad (1.1)$$

where \mathbf{u} and \mathbf{f} are vector functions, are considered. Since the nonlinear term does not interfere with the incompressibility constraint, we mainly focus our attention on the time-dependent Stokes equations written in terms of velocity.

For efficient solution of this problem on parallel computers of IBM Blue Gene/P type we consider an algorithm based on Direction Splitting Method using Chorin – Temam algorithm [13]. If τ is the time-step than Chorin – Temam is just the singular perturbed problem:

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t \mathbf{u}_\varepsilon - \nu \Delta \mathbf{u}_\varepsilon + \nabla p_\varepsilon &= \mathbf{f} && \text{in } \Omega \times [0, T], \\ -\tau \Delta p_\varepsilon + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_\varepsilon &= 0 && \text{in } \Omega \times [0, T], \\ \mathbf{u}_\varepsilon|_{\partial\Omega} = 0, \partial_n p_\varepsilon|_{\partial\Omega} &= 0 && \text{in } [0, T] \text{ and } \mathbf{u}_\varepsilon|_{t=0} = \mathbf{u}_0, p_\varepsilon|_{t=0} = p_0 \text{ in } \Omega. \end{aligned} \quad (1.2)$$

The following perturbation of (1.2) will be considered for the development of the algorithm which will be implementing on IBM Blue Gene/P computer:

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t \mathbf{u}_\varepsilon - \nu \Delta \mathbf{u}_\varepsilon + \nabla p_\varepsilon &= \mathbf{f} && \text{in } \Omega \times [0, T], \\ -\tau \Delta p_\varepsilon + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_\varepsilon &= 0 && \text{in } \Omega \times [0, T], \end{aligned} \quad (1.3)$$

$$\mathbf{u}_\varepsilon|_{\partial\Omega} = 0, \quad p_\varepsilon \in D(A) \quad \text{in } [0, T] \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{u}_\varepsilon|_{t=0} = \mathbf{u}_0, \quad p_\varepsilon|_{t=0} = p_0 \quad \text{in } \Omega.$$

In (1.3) the operator A and his domain $D(A)$ are such that the bilinear form $a(p, q) =: \int_{\Omega} qAp \, d\mathbf{x}$ has the following two properties:

$$A \text{ is symmetric, and} \tag{1.4a}$$

$$\|\nabla q\|_{L^2}^2 \leq a(q, q), \quad \forall q \in D(A). \tag{1.4b}$$

There exist different ways to choose the operator A . For the needs of the algorithm described here and the optimization of the communications between the processors of the IBM Blue Gene/P computer we will define the operator A as $A := (1 - \partial_{xx})(1 - \partial_{yy})(1 - \partial_{zz})$ plus boundary conditions as was mentioned above. The replacement of the Laplace operator with an operator of directions splitting reduced the problem of solving the Poisson equation to the problem of solving series of one-dimensional boundary value problems of second order. The following two algorithms of Crank-Nicolson type are constructed:

(a) Three-steps algorithm (Algorithm I)

(I-1) pressure predictor

$$p^{*,n+\frac{1}{2}} = p^{n-\frac{1}{2}} \tag{1.5}$$

(I-2) velocity update

$$\frac{\xi^{n+1} - \mathbf{u}^n}{\tau} - \nu \Delta \mathbf{u}^n + \nabla p^{*,n+\frac{1}{2}} = \mathbf{f}\left(t^{n+\frac{1}{2}}\right), \quad \xi^{n+1}|_{\partial\Omega} = 0, \tag{1.6}$$

$$\frac{\eta^{n+1} - \xi^{n+1}}{\tau} - \frac{\nu}{2} \partial_{xx}(\eta^{n+1} - \mathbf{u}^n) = \mathbf{0}, \quad \eta^{n+1}|_{x=0,1} = 0, \tag{1.7}$$

$$\frac{\zeta^{n+1} - \eta^{n+1}}{\tau} - \frac{\nu}{2} \partial_{yy}(\zeta^{n+1} - \mathbf{u}^n) = \mathbf{0}, \quad \zeta^{n+1}|_{y=0,1} = 0, \tag{1.8}$$

$$\frac{\mathbf{u}^{n+1} - \zeta^{n+1}}{\tau} - \frac{\nu}{2} \partial_{zz}(\mathbf{u}^{n+1} - \mathbf{u}^n) = \mathbf{0}, \quad \mathbf{u}^{n+1}|_{z=0,1} = 0, \tag{1.9}$$

Remark: In the 2-D version of the algorithm equation (1.9) is replaced by $\mathbf{u}^{n+1} = \zeta^{n+1}$.

(I-3) pressure update

$$\psi - \partial_{xx}\psi = -\frac{1}{\tau} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}^{n+1}, \quad \partial_x \psi|_{x=0,1} = 0, \tag{1.10}$$

$$\varphi - \partial_{yy}\varphi = \psi, \quad \partial_y \varphi|_{y=0,1} = 0, \tag{1.11}$$

$$p^{n+\frac{1}{2}} - \partial_{zz}p^{n+\frac{1}{2}} = \varphi, \quad \partial_z p^{n+\frac{1}{2}}|_{z=0,1} = 0, \tag{1.12}$$

(b) Four-steps algorithm (Algorithm II)

(II-1) pressure predictor

$$p^{*,n+\frac{1}{2}} = 2p^{n-\frac{1}{2}} - p^{n-\frac{3}{2}} \tag{1.13}$$

(II-2) velocity update

$$\frac{\xi^{n+1} - \mathbf{u}^n}{\tau} - \nu \Delta \mathbf{u}^n + \nabla p^{*,n+\frac{1}{2}} = \mathbf{f}\left(t^{n+\frac{1}{2}}\right), \quad \xi^{n+1}|_{\partial\Omega} = 0, \tag{1.14}$$

$$\frac{\eta^{n+1} - \xi^{n+1}}{\tau} - \frac{\nu}{2} \partial_{xx}(\eta^{n+1} - \mathbf{u}^n) = \mathbf{0}, \quad \eta^{n+1}|_{x=0,1} = 0, \quad (1.15)$$

$$\frac{\zeta^{n+1} - \eta^{n+1}}{\tau} - \frac{\nu}{2} \partial_{yy}(\zeta^{n+1} - \mathbf{u}^n) = \mathbf{0}, \quad \zeta^{n+1}|_{y=0,1} = 0, \quad (1.16)$$

$$\frac{\mathbf{u}^{n+1} - \zeta^{n+1}}{\tau} - \frac{\nu}{2} \partial_{zz}(\mathbf{u}^{n+1} - \mathbf{u}^n) = \mathbf{0}, \quad \mathbf{u}^{n+1}|_{z=0,1} = 0, \quad (1.17)$$

Remark: In the 2-D version of the algorithm equation (17) is replaced by $\mathbf{u}^{n+1} = \zeta^{n+1}$.

(II-3) penalty step

$$\psi - \partial_{xx}\psi = -\frac{1}{\tau} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}^{n+1}, \quad \partial_x \psi|_{x=0,1} = 0, \quad (1.18)$$

$$\varphi - \partial_{yy}\varphi = \psi, \quad \partial_y \psi|_{y=0,1} = 0, \quad (1.19)$$

$$\Phi^{n+\frac{1}{2}} - \partial_{zz}\Phi^{n+\frac{1}{2}} = \varphi, \quad \partial_z \Phi^{n+\frac{1}{2}}|_{z=0,1} = 0, \quad (1.20)$$

(I-3) pressure update

$$p^{n+\frac{1}{2}} = p^{n-\frac{1}{2}} + \Phi^{n+\frac{1}{2}} - \chi \nu \nabla \cdot \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{u}^{n+1} + \mathbf{u}^n). \quad (1.21)$$

The numerical experiments showed that the best value for the parameter χ is $\chi \approx 0.95$. This algorithm is computationally efficient and has a computational complexity of an explicit scheme and being at the same time unconditionally stable. In the proposed algorithm, three diagonal systems of linear algebraic equations must be solved. There is no need of matrix transposition which can be found in other algorithms which realize direction splitting methods. The convergence analysis and the analysis of the computer output results show that the error of the here presented direction splitting method is of the same order as the error of the classical projection schemes. In the same time, the computational complexity of the direction splitting algorithm is better because it requires $O(N)$ arithmetic operations on each time step while the Fast Furrier Transform (FFT) requires $O(N \log_2 N)$ operations at each time step. Moreover, the new approach has significant advantages in implementation on parallel computers with distributed memory.

1.3. Computer implementation and tests

The software tools which are needed for the implementation of the presented above algorithm on computer architectures of the IBM Blue Gene/P type are developed [2, 5, 12]. The codes are written using C^{++} . For the communications between the processors the standard MPI (Message Passing Interface) is used. The new development software is organized as a computer library on the IBM Blue Gene/P computer located in Sofia and it is able to be used when incompressible Navier-Stokes equations are solved on this computer.

The presented output results are for solving the non-stationary Stokes equation. **LAPACK** subroutines **DPTRF** and **DPTTS2** are used for solving the tree-diagonal systems of linear equations for the velocity update and pressure correction in each sub-domain.

The algorithm is tested up to 1024 processors (4096 cores). Some comparison analysis of the CPU time, speed-up and efficiency on IBM Blue Gene/P computer and Sooner cluster (Linux cluster on the base of 486 Dell PowerEdge 1950 III four-cores nodes; see <http://www.oscer.ou.edu/> for more details) are done. Some of the output

results obtained in these experiments are presented in the following three tables. The CPU times are measured in seconds by using the MPI function `MPI_Wtime`, the speed-up is defined by $S_p = T_1/T_p$, where T_p is the time for the execution of the algorithm using p processors (cores); the efficiency on p processors is defined as $E_p = S_p/p$.

Table 1.1 CPU time for execution of the 3D Stokes problem on IBM Blue Gene/P computer

Number of cores	n_x									
	120	120	120	240	240	240	480	480	480	960
	n_y									
	120	120	240	240	240	480	480	480	960	960
n_z										
	120	240	240	240	480	480	480	960	960	960
1	1623.6	3248.3	6582.4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
128	12.5	24.4	48.5	123.1	190.0	377.8	829.6	1721.6	3497.0	6986.4
512	3.7	7.0	13.6	26.8	51.7	127.1	199.7	409.6	847.4	1768.8
1024	2.7	5.0	9.6	15.5	30.0	58.4	135.3	212.2	430.9	892.9
2048	1.9	3.6	5.8	9.3	17.9	32.6	62.2	166.2	226.1	493.2
4096	1.5	2.3	3.7	6.2	11.2	19.4	37.2	70.9	186.8	311.1

Table 1.2. The speed-up achieved during the IBM Blue Gene/P and Dell PowerEdge cluster runs for 3D Stokes problem.

n_x	n_y	n_z	Number of cores									
			2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024
Dell PowerEdge cluster												
120	120	120	2.01	4.00	5.63	10.92	29.95	63.09	138.47	217.22		
120	120	240	1.95	3.04	3.87	7.73	22.28	60.13	114.60	211.74		
120	240	240	2.00	3.02	3.67	7.16	16.68	47.71	109.54	219.01		
240	240	240	1.94	3.04	3.45	7.65	17.50	50.80	97.45	227.97		
240	240	480	1.94	2.94	3.31	7.26	15.80	35.41	68.88	178.18		
240	480	480	2.00	2.88	3.42	7.11	15.65	33.53	63.76	142.45		
IBM Blue Gene/P computer												
120	120	120	2.11	4.38	9.15	14.09	35.75	69.87	129.82	230.43	435.96	594.70
120	120	240	2.03	4.26	8.75	18.46	27.54	70.88	132.86	235.95	465.97	646.38
120	240	240	2.02	4.06	8.42	18.73	36.82	55.95	135.78	250.18	482.82	687.72

Table 1.3. The parallel efficiency achieved during the IBM Blue Gene/P and Dell PowerEdge cluster runs for 3D Stokes problem.

n_x	n_y	n_z	Number of cores											
			2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	4096
Dell PowerEdge cluster														
120	120	120	1.007	1.001	0.703	0.691	0.936	1.025	1.082	0.849				
120	120	240	0.975	0.759	0.484	0.483	0.709	0.939	0.902	0.827				
120	240	240	0.997	0.753	0.457	0.446	0.520	0.757	0.886	0.853				
240	240	240	0.967	0.757	0.430	0.477	0.545	0.795	0.766	0.888				
240	240	480	0.970	0.734	0.413	0.453	0.493	0.552	0.543	0.695				
240	480	480	1.002	0.715	0.424	0.441	0.485	0.520	0.500	0.552				
IBM Blue Gene/P computer														
120	120	120	1.055	1.096	1.143	0.881	1.117	1.092	1.014	0.900	0.851	0.581	0.420	0.267
120	120	240	1.014	1.064	1.094	1.154	0.861	1.108	1.038	0.922	0.910	0.631	0.439	0.340
120	240	240	1.008	1.015	1.052	1.171	1.151	0.874	1.061	0.977	0.943	0.672	0.557	0.435

The runs were done using 1 – 256 Dell PowerEdge cluster nodes and 128 – 1024 nodes of the IBM Blue Gene/p computer with using *mpirun* with options *-mode dual* and *-mode vn*. The empty boxes in the tables above are due to the fact that the memory of the IBM Blue Gene/P node is 2 GB but the memory needed is larger. The analysis of the output results show that for the problems with big dimensions the efficiency achieved on IBM Blue Gene/P computer is much larger than this achieved on Dell PowerEdge cluster. The superlinear speed-up which can be seen in some places in the tables is due to the better use of the cache memories of the processors (L3 cache is 8MB for IBM Blue Gene/P computer). The decreased efficiency which can be seen in some of runs shows that the use of the standard MPI communication subroutines is not very efficient between cores in one and the same node.

2. Scalable mathematical methods for FEM applications on massively parallel computers and software tools for their implementation

2.1. Introduction

The supercomputer applications are based on the recent achievements in the field of the scientific computing, including: FEM; numerical homogenization methods which allow to make transition between different physical models; sensitivity analysis; algorithms with adaptive time-stepping, etc. The core issue in this research is development of software tools for MPI clusters and massively parallel computers. More than 70% of the computational time using in the computer models of real life problems and phenomena is for solving linear algebra problems. This percent increase with the increase of the problem size. In these cases preconditioned iterative solution methods are used. Robust algebraic multigrid and multilevel methods are among the most important achievements in this area. Our aim is to develop scalable algorithms and the corresponding software tools for solving problems with discrete dimensions of several billions of unknowns using the IBM Blue Gene/P parallel computer. Several different aspects of efficient parallel implementation of FEM are included:

- FEM discretization on: (a) grids with voxel structure; (b) unstructured grids;
- FEM method for: (a) elliptic (stationary) problems; (b) parabolic (non-stationary) problems;
- Software tools for: (a) linear model (linear partial differential equations (PDEs)); (b) nonlinear model (nonlinear PDEs)

2.2. Efficient parallel implementation of FEM on grids with voxel structures

Let us consider the following PDE in a cubic domain Ω with boundary $\partial\Omega$:

$$\rho c \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot k \nabla T + J \cdot E - h_{bl}(T - T_{bl}), \quad (2.1)$$

where

- Ω is the entire domain of the model and $\partial\Omega$ is its boundary;
- ρ is the density (kg/m^3);
- c is the specific heat (J/kg K);
- k is the thermal conductivity (W/m K);
- J is the current density (A/m);
- E is the electric field intensity (V/m);
- t is the time (s);
- T is the temperature (C);
- T_{bl} is the blood temperature (37°C);
- W_{bl} is the blood perfusion (1/s);
- $h_{bl} = \rho_{bl} c_{bl} w_{bl}$ is the convective heat transfer coefficient accounting for the blood perfusion in the model.

The term $J \cdot E$ in (2.1) represents the thermal energy arising from the current flow and the term $h_{bl}(T - T_{bl})$ accounts for the heat loss due to perfusion.

For the numerical solution FEM simulation in space is used [3, 11]. Linear conforming elements are chosen in this study. They provide a simple implementation in combination with a guaranteed optimal convergence rate and parallel scalability of the applied algebraic multigrid (AMG) preconditioner. In order to apply the linear FEM discretization to the voxel domain, each voxel is split into six tetrahedra. To solve the bio-heat equation, after the space discretization, the time derivative is discretized via finite differences and the backward Euler scheme is used ([10]). The preconditioner which is used here is BoomerAMG of HYPRE code of the Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (LLNL), USA.

The parallel efficiency of the proposed algorithm has been studied by computer experiments on the IBM Blue Gene/P computer located in Sofia, Bulgaria. Three variants of the problem domain partitioning were considered – one, two and three dimensional (see Fig. 2.1).

The first realization the distribution between processors only on one direction was used and the following restrictions on the parallel efficiency were observed:

- the number of the used processors cannot be greater than the number of the unknowns in one of the directions;
- when the number of the unknowns is huge than the memory requirements increase very quickly and they cannot be satisfied;
- the computer topology (the communication scheme between the processors) of the IBM Blue Gene/P computer, which is three-dimensional grid or three-dimensional torus, cannot be used efficiently.

Fig. 2.1 Domain partitioning between computer processors – one, two and three dimensional

These difficulties were overcome by the improving this first algorithm with the possibilities to use one, two or three dimensional partitioning in each of the coordinate axis (see Fig. 2.1).

Linear conforming finite elements are used for space discretization of (2.1) while the implicit Euler method is used in time. For solving of the huge systems of linear algebraic equations which appear after the discretization the Preconditioned Conjugate Gradient Method (PCGM) is used. The preconditioner used is the parallel implementation of algebraic multigrid method Boomer AMG from HYPRE library which is developed in the Livermore National Laboratory of USA.

Computer tests on the IBM Blue Gene/P computer located in Sofia were done with the three different ways of domain partitioning shown on Fig. 2.1. Some of the output results are presented on Table. 2.1,

Table 2.1 *Parallel CPU times and efficiency according to different partitioning and runnings*

<i>Domain</i>	N_p	=	P_x	X	P_y	X	P_z	<i>Unknowns</i>	N_{it}	<i>CPU time</i>	<i>Efficiency</i>
127 x 127 x 127	8	=	8	X	1	X	1	2 097 152	161	1 225.00 s	
255 x 255 x 255	64	=	64	X	1	X	1	16 777 216	128	5 951.08 s	21 %
511 x 511 x 511	512	=	512	X	1	X	1	134 217 728	-	> 24 hours	< 2%
127 x 127 x 127	8	=	4	X	2	X	1	2 097 152	167	1 137.83 s	
255 x 255 x 255	64	=	8	X	8	X	1	16 777 216	129	1 203.29 s	95 %
511 x 511 x 511	512	=	32	X	16	X	1	134 217 728	114	1 581.13 s	72 %
127 x 127 x 127	8	=	2	X	2	X	2	2 097 152	167	1 137.91 s	
255 x 255 x 255	64	=	4	X	4	X	4	16 777 216	128	1 062.30 s	107 %
511 x 511 x 511	512	=	8	X	8	X	8	134 217 728	114	1 155.08 s	99 %

where the following notations are used:

- N_p – number of the processors used;
- P_x, P_y, P_z – number of the subdomains in directions x, y and z ;
- N_{it} – number of iterations in the PCGM.

These results show a significant improvement of the parallel efficiency when the computational domain is divided into subdomains in directions of the three coordinate axes. Moreover, the size of the data should be transmitted between the processors decrease significant which leads to a significant decreasing of the communication time. It should be mentioned, that these three-directions dividing match the IBM Blue Gene/P topology, which allows the communications in all the three directions to be done in parallel. The last fact further decrease the communication time and increase the efficiency of the algorithm.

2.2. Parallel implementation of FEM on unstructured grids

New software tools for parallel implementation of FEM on unstructured grids were developed. They can be structured in the following four groups:

- *Transformation of a mesh written in NetGen format in parallel format.* The parallel format allows fast reading and fast writing of the mesh from parallel computer codes. Each processor reads and writes only its local mesh data in file for use only from this processor. **bzip2** compression of I/O files is supported which not only decrease the size of the transmitting data but accelerates the I/O process. This is very important in the cases of using relatively slow file systems.
- *Grid (mesh) compression.* The accuracy of the computations depends on the typical size of the finite elements. Therefore, the mesh compression improves the accuracy of the computations. A uniform compression of the initial unstructured mesh is realized.
- *Renumbering of the grid nodes.* The grid nodes are renumbering in the way that the local for each processor elements to be with serial numbers. This allows in the next steps fast access to data corresponding to the

local nodes by direct addressing. In addition, this numbering allows an efficient check whether a node is local or not. Most of the computer libraries, including *HYPRE*, guess just this numbering.

- *Mesh division via ParMETIS.* *ParMETIS* is a parallel computer library for fast graph partitioning, which minimizes the subdomains interfaces. This leads to decreasing of the communications when some complicated problems are solved. *ParMETIS* gives information about the elements division. The element's vertices are to be separated additionally. The information is in the terms of compliance “element – subdivision number”. The necessary geometrical information is transmitted to the corresponding processors.

The new development software is organized as a computer library on the IBM Blue Gene/P computer located in Sofia and it is able to be used.

The information about mesh partitioning when 512 IBM Blue Gene/P processors in VN mode are used and local compression is applied can be seen on Table 2.2.

Table 2.2 *Mesh division when 512 processors are used*

	<i>Number of the elements</i>	<i>Local vertices</i>	<i>Foreign vertices</i>	<i>Edges</i>
<i>Total number</i>	904 834 560	150 943 232		770 825
<i>In average</i>	1 767 255	294 811	15 044	1 505
<i>Minimum</i>	777 582	139 058	63	0
<i>Maximum</i>	1 843 442	316 566	27 922	9 435

Parallel algorithm for discretization of the Laplace equation with linear (tetrahedrons) finite elements on unstructured grids and solving the systems of linear algebraic equations with PCGM where the preconditioner is chosen to be the parallel multigrid *BoomerAMG* from *Hypre* computer library is developed. The new algorithm was tested on the IBM Blue Gene/P computer located in Sofia (Bulgaria) in VN mode. Different meshes both on size and on density, with the fines one with about 150 million nodes and 900 million tetrahedrons were used. In VN mode in each computer node four MPI processes are working. The number of maximal computer nodes were used is equal to 1024 (4096 processors). It should be mentioned that up to 256 nodes the communication grid is three dimensional mesh, and when 512 and 1024 nodes are used – the communication grid is torus.

2.3. Implementation of the developed software tools in *Elmer* code

Elmer is an open source code with FEM applications in the field of solid mechanics, fluid mechanics, electromagnetic, heat transfer and acoustics.

Hypre is a computer library consisting of high performance preconditioners including parallel implementation of multigrid methods on structured and unstructured meshes. On the *Hypre* base simulations in security, environmental studies, energetic, biology etc. are developed.

BoomerAMG is a parallel realization of the algebraic multigrid method. It can be used as a method for solving systems of linear algebraic equations and as a preconditioner inside other iteration methods.

Integration of Hypre and BoomerAMG with Elmer. The subroutine *ElmerSolver_mpi* from *fem* package of *Elmer* code has feature to use subroutines from the *Hypre* library. The including is via the following line in the input file of the code:

```
Linear System Use Hypre = True
```

The only iteration method from *Hypre* library which can be used is the Stabilized Conjugate Gradient Method known as *BiCGStab*. It is able to be done via the following lines:

Linear System Solver = "Iterative"

Linear System Iterative Method = "BiCGStab".

Several preconditioners from **Hypre** library can be used together with **BiCGStab**:

- Incomplete factorization – **ILU**;
- Approximate inverse matrix – **ParaSails**;
- Algebraic multigrid – **BoomerAMG**.

In order to use **BoomerAMG** the following line should be added to the input file:

Linear System Preconditioning = "BoomerAMG".

When **BoomerAMG** is used as a preconditioner then in the input file of the subroutine the following BoomerAMG parameters must be prescribed:

- *BoomerAMG Relax Type = <Integer>*
- *BoomerAMG Coarsen Type = <Integer>*
- *BoomerAMG Num Sweeps = <Integer>*
- *Boomeramg Max Levels = <Integer>*
- *BoomerAMG Interpolation Type = <Integer>*
- *BoomerAMG Smooth Type = <Integer>*
- *BoomerAMG Cycle Type = <Integer>*
- *BoomerAMG Num Functions = <Integer>*

Packages installation.

Hypre: In order to use the Hypre library in Elmer code the library must be compiled as dynamical one and this action can be done by the following commands:

```
$ ./configure --enable-shared
```

```
$ make
```

```
$ make install
```

The following extra lines are to be added in the code;

```
$ export MPI_HOME="full path to MPI"
```

```
$ export HYPRE="full path to the Hypre installation"
```

```
$ export CPPFLAGS="-I$HYPRE/include"
```

```
$ ./configure --with-mpi=yes --with-mpi-dir = $MPI_HOME \  
--with-hypre="-L$HYPRE/lib -lHYPRE"
```

```
$ make
```

```
$ make install
```

2.4. Scalability studies of the *Elmer* code and *Hipre* library

The scalability of two iteration methods on the base of CGM for solving systems of linear algebraic equations was studied. The linear systems are obtained after the discretization of the Poisson equation on regular and unstructured tetrahedron meshes in the unit cube. The parallel tests were done on a cluster of 16 cores (processors *Intel Xeon X5560 @2.8Ghz, 24GB RAM*). The tests were done with increasing the problem size proportional to the number of processors used.

Regular tetrahedron mesh. The initial mesh was obtained by the division of the unit cube on 128 x 128 x 128 small cubes and subsequent division of each small cube on six tetrahedrons. The output results according to the number of the iterations and the CPU times can be found in Table 2.3

Table 2.3 Scalability experiments for regular mesh

Number of processors	Number of iterations ILU0	CPU time ILU0 [s]	Number of iterations BoomerAMG	CPU time BoomerAMG [s]
1	125	462	-	-
2	142	276	8	319
4	172	178	9	215
8	217	125	11	123
16	298	64	15	67
32	341	34	18	37

The analysis of the output results shows that for this discrete size the two used methods for preconditioning (incomplete factorization – ILU0 and algebraic multilevel – BoomerAMG) have similar CPU times. In both methods the increasing of the number of the processors leads to increase in the number of the iterations.

Unstructured tetrahedron mesh. In order to use Elmer on parallel machines the mesh must be in a special parallel format. The tool *ElmerGrid* which is a part of Elmer code for generation of such grids is sequential and this restricts its scalability. In order to overcome these shortcomings, a new parallel software tool was developed. As an input in this tool meshes generated by the mesh generator *NetGen* are used. The next step in the algorithm is to partition these meshes on parts by using *ParMetis* parallel library. The grid in the initial cube consists of 2 196 992 vertices and 12 582 912 tetrahedrons. The output results according to the number of the iterations and the CPU times can be found in Table 2.4.

Table 2.4 Scalability experiments for unstructured mesh

Number processors	Number of iterations ILU0	CPU time ILU0 [s]	Number of iterations BoomerAMG	CPU time BoomerAMG [s]
1	124	462	-	-
2	144	279	8	316
4	172	178	9	206
8	219	129	12	135
16	298	63	17	76
32	341	34	20	42

The analysis of the output results shows that for this problem size the method of incomplete factorization is faster irrespective of the significantly higher number of iterations. The efficiency of ILU0 when 32 processors are used is 42%. When the algebraic multigrid method is used increasing in number of the iterations can be seen too and the **BoomerAMG** efficiency on 32 processors is 50%. The CPU times of the both methods are almost the same. On the base of some theoretical studies one can expect that when the discrete problem size is increased then **BoomerAMG** will become relatively faster.

2.5 Testing Elmer code on an IBM Blue Gene/P computer

The developed scalable tools for FEM applications are incorporated and tested within the Elmer environment which was the **first time successfully ported to IBM Blue Gene/P architecture**.

In order to install Elmer FEM on the IBM Blue Gene/P a decent FORTRAN compiler is needed. The available compilers from the *GCC* suite, and IBM XL ones could not compile Elmer's source code. *GCC* compiler *gfortran version 4.1.2* just does not support enough Fortran90 & Fortran95 language features. IBM Fortran compilers could compile the source code only without optimizations. Compiling even with basic optimizations (*-O flag*) made the compiler to hang for some source files. We have compiled a newer version of *GCC* - *version 4.3.0*. The newer *gfortran* managed to compile Elmer FEM flawlessly. During the Elmer code compilation the support for *Hypre* library is included.

Running Elmer on the compute nodes requires setting the environment variable *LD_LIBRARY_PATH* to the path where the newer runtime libraries (from *gcc 4.3.0*) are situated.

A stationary heat conduction equation on a cylindrical rod, composed of two materials (see the picture on the right) is considered. Dirichlet boundary conditions on both ends of the rod are applied. The mesh is generated with the automatic 3d tetrahedral mesh generator *NetGen*, then partitioned using the MPI-based parallel library

ParMETIS that implements a variety of algorithms for partitioning unstructured graphs, meshes, and for computing fill-reducing orderings of sparse matrices and finally, transformed to the Elmer mesh format. New software tools for parallel implementation of FEM on unstructured grids were developed. They can be structured in the following four groups: (i) Transformation of a mesh written in *NetGen* format in parallel format; (ii) Grid (mesh) compression; (iii)

Renumbering of the grid nodes; (iv) Mesh division via *ParMETIS*. Tests with varying thermal conductivity jump between the two materials were performed. The advantages of the parallel AMG (Algebraic MultiGrid) compared to the more commonly used parallel incomplete factorization (ILU) are well expressed in the case of coefficient jumps and unstructured grids (see Tables 2.5 – 2.7 for different jumps of the coefficients). A set of comparative analysis for parallel scalability of Elmer on Blue Gene/P and a MPI cluster are also performed to illustrate how the problems with porting of Elmer are solved including the new developed tools for parallel mesh refinement.

Table 2.5 Number of iterations and CPU time for stationary heat conduction equation on a cylindrical rod without coefficients jump (P – number of processor nodes, N – number of unknowns)

P	N	Iterations ILU	Time in sec. ILU	Iterations BoomerAMG	Time in sec. BoomerAMG
128	1 678 336	580	62.2	20	37.4
128	13 426 688	818	522.0	22	303.0
256	1 678 336	675	51.2	20	31.6
256	13 426 688	610	307.0	23	216.0
512	1 678 336	619	48.7	20	33.9
512	13 426 688	2521	484.0	24	186.0
1024	1 678 336	761	91.4	20	34.6
1024	13 426 688	642	254.0	22	192.0
1024	107 413 504	694	1947.0	20	1511.0

Table 2.6. Number of iterations and CPU time for stationary heat conduction equation on a cylindrical rod with coefficients jump of 10 (P – number of processor nodes, N – number of unknowns)

P	N	Iterations ILU	Time in sec. ILU	Iterations BoomerAMG	Time in sec. BoomerAMG
128	1 678 336	922	75.8	20	36.6
128	13 426 688	1763	787.9	22	327.0
256	1 678 336	1180	59.9	20	30.2
256	13 426 688	1361	441.1	23	256.0
512	1 678 336	1556	64.84	20	41.2
512	13 426 688	4779	749.7	24	191.0
1024	1 678 336	1938	98.5	20	30.6
1024	13 426 688	1541	297.1	22	205.0
1024	107 413 504	1232	2340.0	20	1563.0

Table 2.7. Number of iterations and CPU time for stationary heat conduction equation on a cylindrical rod with coefficient jump of 100 (P – number of processor nodes, N – number of unknowns)

P	N	Iterations ILU	Time in sec. ILU	Iterations BoomerAMG	Time in sec. BoomerAMG
128	1 678 336	569	58.8	20	38.1
128	13 426 688	999	563.0	22	321.0
256	1 678 336	624	42.2	20	30.2
256	13 426 688	519	287.2	23	243.0
512	1 678 336	886	43.6	20	34.2
512	13 426 688	2949	512.0	24	183.0
1024	1 678 336	889	65.8	20	45.0
1024	13 426 688	698	172.4	22	188.0
1024	107 413 504	728	1956.0	20	1461.0

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